

A Short Synthesis of Undecan-3-one, 5-Methyl-5(*E*)-hepten-2-one and 4,6-Dimethyl-6(*E*)-nonen-3-one

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Undecan-3-one (**3a**) is one of the odoriferous components¹ of the seaweed *Diclyoteris membranaca* and also a component of the alarm pheromone of major workers of the African ant *Decophylla longinoda*². Jones *et al.*³ isolated 4,6-dimethyl-6(*E*)-nonen-3-one (**3b**) as a principal component from the defensive secretion of *L. longipes*, a species of opillionids and assigned structure (**3b**) on the basis of spectral data and synthesis. Watanabe *et al.*⁴ synthesised 5-methyl-5(*E*)-hepten-2-one (**3c**), an important intermediate in organic synthesis. We report herein a stereoselective synthesis of **3a-c** in good yields (Scheme 1).

- a: R = Et, R' = H, R'' = n-C₆H₁₃, R₁ = H
b: R = Et, R' = Me, R'' = C₂H₅CH=C(CH₃), R₁ = CH₃
c: R = Me, R' = H, R'' = CH₃CH=C(CH₃), R₁ = H

Scheme 1

The hydrazones **1a-c** were prepared by treating the corresponding ketones with *N,N*-dimethylhydrazine⁵. Alkylation⁶ of α -lithiosalts of **1a/1b/1c** with 1-bromoheptane/2-methyl-1-bromo-2(*E*)-pentene/2-methyl-1-bromo-2(*E*)-butene (prepared by phosphonate Wittig reaction⁷) respectively, using freshly prepared LDA at -78° in THF gave the hydrazones **2a-c** respectively. Oxidative hydrolysis⁸ of **2a-c** with sodium metaperiodate in methanol at pH 7 furnished **3a-c** respectively. The spectral data of the synthesised products were found to be consistent with those reported in literature^{3,4}.

Experimental

Microanalyses were carried out in the Microanalytical

Section of R.S.I.C., Panjab University, Chandigarh. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrometer using thin liquid film, ¹H nmr spectra (CCl₄ or CDCl₃) at 90 MHz on a Varian EM-390 spectrometer. Silica gel 100–200 mesh (Acme) was used for column chromatography. Tlc was performed on silica gel G. Unless otherwise stated, all the organic extracts were dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate.

Undecan-3-one-N,N-dimethylhydrazone (**2a**), *4,6*-dimethyl-6(*E*)-nonen-3-one, *N,N*-dimethylhydrazone (**2b**) and *5*-methyl-5(*E*)-hepten-2-one-*N,N*-dimethylhydrazone (**2c**): To a stirred solution of LDA (11.07 mmol, freshly prepared from diisopropylamine and 2 *N*, *n*-BuLi) in THF (10 ml) at 0° and under N₂ atmosphere, was added dropwise a solution of **1a** (1.14 g, 10 mmol)/**1b** (1.29 g, 10 mmol)/**1c** (1.0 g, 10 mmol) in THF (10 ml). The solution was kept for additional 20 h at 0°, cooled at -78° and a solution of 1-bromo-heptane (1.78 g, 10 mmol)/1-bromo-2-methyl-2(*E*)-pentene (1.62 g, 10 mmol)/1-bromo-2-methyl-2(*E*)-butene (1.49 g, 10 mmol) was respectively added dropwise to it with stirring. The reaction mixture was kept at the same temperature for 1 h, allowed to come to room temperature, poured on a mixture of water and dichloromethane (3 : 1), extracted with dichloromethane and dried. Evaporation of the solvent yielded the products: **2a** (2.8 g, 85%), (Found: C, 73.20; H, 13.10. Requires: C, 73.58; H, 13.21%); ν_{\max} (neat) 2 860, 1 690, 1 440, 1 390, 1 360, 1 100 cm⁻¹; δ (CCl₄) 0.85–1.1 (6H, t, 2×CH₃), 1.3 (12H, b s), 2.2–2.4 (10H, s + m, (–CH₂–C(=NNMe₂))–CH₂); **2b** (1.42 g, 86%), (Found: C, 74.10; H, 12.20. Requires: C, 74.21; H, 12.46%); ν_{\max} 3 000, 2 900, 1 680, 1 640, 1 460, 1 380 cm⁻¹; δ (CCl₄) 0.8–1.1 (9H, m), 1.6 (3H, s), 1.8–2.4 (13H, s + m), 4.9–5.3 (1H, m); **2c** (1.4 g, 84%), (Found: C, 71.20; H, 11.70. Requires: C, 71.36; H, 11.98%); ν_{\max} 3 015, 2 920, 1 680, 1 470, 1 370 cm⁻¹; δ (CCl₄) 1.6 (6H, b s), 1.9 (3H, s), 2.1–2.3 (10H, s + m), 5.0–5.4 (1H, m).

Undecan-3-one (**3a**), *4,6*-dimethyl-6(*E*)-nonen-3-one (**3b**) and *5*-methyl-5(*E*)-hepten-2-one (**3c**): To a stirred solution of the hydrazone **2a** (1.0 g, 4.73 mmol)/**2b** (1.0 g, 4.7 mmol) and **2c** (0.8 g, 4.7 mmol) in methanol (70 ml), were added the phosphate buffer (1 *N*, pH 7, 14.2 mmol) and a solution of sodium metaperiodate (2.23 g, 10.4 mmol) in water (24 ml) at 25° respectively. Gas evolution and pre-

cipitation of sodium iodate ensured rapidly. On completion of hydrolysis (tlc monitoring), the reaction mixture was filtered. The filtrate was diluted with water, extracted with dichloromethane and dried. Solvent evaporation followed by column chromatography of the residue over silica gel using petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) as eluent afforded the products : **3a**, (0.61 g, 81%), (Found : C, 77.40; H, 12.50. Requires : C, 77.65; H, 12.94%); ν_{\max} (neat) 2 860, 1 705, 1 460, 1 430, 1 340 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.9–1.1 (6H, m), 1.4 (12H, b s), 2.2–2.5 (4H, m); **3b** (0.62 g, 78%), (Found : C, 76.30; H, 11.60. Requires : C, 76.46; H, 11.90%); ν_{\max} (neat) 2 990, 2 900, 1 715, 1 460, 1 375, 1 055, 1 025 and 970 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.8–1.1 (9H, m), 1.6 (3H, s), 1.8–2.9 (7H, m), 5.1 (1H, t); **3c** (0.4 g, 67%), (Found : C, 75.90; H, 10.80. Requires : C, 76.19; H, 11.11%); ν_{\max} (neat) 3 010, 2 915, 1 720, 1 680, 1 455, 1 375 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 1.6 (6H, b s), 1.9 (3H, s), 2.1–2.3 (4H, m), 5.0–5.4 (1H, m).

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